

iJEResearch

International Journal of Education and Research

Vol-1, Number 2, September- 2022 | Peer-Reviewed Journal

ISSN 2764-9733 | ijerresearch.org

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10213388

CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

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ABSTRACT

Organizations began to recognize their direct responsibility in relation to social problems and adopt actions to address them. The contemporary definition of CSR includes the company's commitment to society and humanity, based on accountability for its performance, considering the use of resources that do not belong to it. Terms such as corporate citizenship and corporate governance were also introduced, highlighting the need for socially responsible and sustainable practices in the long term. Where values and ethical issues can go beyond "profit". In this scenario, the ability to make effective decisions is fundamental to the success and survival of organizations. By adopting an ethical stance, companies strengthen their reputation and build a relationship of trust. Analyzing social delimitations, the issue of ethics that incorporates such actions, and how such a movement emerges in the face of companies in Brazil.

KEYWORDS : Responsibility; Citizenship; Need; Resources; Decisions.

INTRODUCTION

The evolution of civilization throughout history has been marked by continuous processes of transformation. According to Oliveira (2013), a change of significant proportions triggered by the Industrial Revolution caused profound changes, where there was a notable transformation in production systems, boosting manufacturing activities and generating substantial impacts on the economy, social standards and, inevitably, the environment. .

Concern about the ramifications of this development model gained prominence following the publication, in 1972, of the report “Limits to Growth” by the Club of Rome. This report warned of population expansion, agricultural production, industrial production, use of natural resources and pollution as driving factors for growth, but also as limiting factors if they were not properly controlled. Concern about the consequences of this growth model grew on an international scale, leading the United Nations (UN) to introduce the issue on the global agenda, with the aim of seeking development that minimized the negative effects. Thus, the Sustainable Development proposal emerged, launched in 1987 based on the Brundtland Report . This development model aims to balance social, economic and environmental needs, with the aim of ensuring the sustainability of natural resources and the planet.

In this context, companies, industries and various productive sectors are called upon to adapt, whether due to legal impositions, the pressure of society's demands or consumer awareness. This call gave rise to the concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).

However, also when delimiting the ethical issue that involves a business, which can be linked to the moral principles of companies, in this sense acted as guidelines for how a company conducts itself in its operations. In many ways, the same guidelines that individuals use to behave acceptably in personal and professional settings also apply to businesses. When acting ethically, be in a way that determines what is “right” and what is “wrong”.

CSR has a substantial impact on company operations and performance. In this sense, it is justified to

understand these implications as a way to improve the efficiency, competitiveness and sustainability of organizations.

The objective of this article is to understand the tangible aspects that can promote and understand CSR in Brazilian companies. Analyzing social delimitations, the issue of ethics that incorporates such actions, and how such a movement emerges in the face of companies in Brazil.

Given the above, how can Corporate Social Responsibility impact the socioeconomic development of companies in Brazil?

The research method is based on the form of bibliographical research, which according to Gil (2012) helps guide the search, providing guidelines and relevant keywords related to the topic of interest. With this, words were defined that could help in the context relevant to the topic, thus researched on: Corporate Social Responsibility; Corporate Environmental Responsibility; Sustainability; Sustainability in companies; Sustainability Tripods; Sustainable Companies; Business ethics; Ethics Socio-environmental; Environmental awareness; Corporate social responsibility; Sustainable practices in organizations.

Data collection was done entirely on the internet, both on Google and Google Scholar, as a way of delimiting a tool with the same database, in this sense, better aggregating the research based on the keywords listed. From the perspective of temporal construction, the publications had a long order over the years, starting in 1970 until 2023.

DEVELOPMENT

Corporate Social Responsibility

According to Dias (2011), the notion of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) began to develop in response to these growing social demands for greater environmental responsibility and an improvement in society's quality of life. The United Nations Conference on Environment and Development, known as Rio/92, highlighted the importance of companies in unsustainable development and emphasized the need for ethical and responsible

standards, SA 8000, AHSAS 18001, AA 1000, the Earth Charter, the Millennium Goals and Targets, the UN Global Compact, ILO Conventions, Ethos Social Responsibility Indicators and the GRI (Global Reporting initiatives).

The duality of the company as an economic and social entity is highlighted, since, while it seeks to obtain profits, it also has social functions defined by the State, in accordance with ethical principles established in the Federal Constitution of 1988. In this context, the Federal Constitution establishes general principles of economic activity, aimed at promoting a dignified existence and social justice. The company as a social institution has the primary responsibility of producing goods and providing services to meet the needs of society, distributing wealth through the creation of jobs and contributing taxes to national development. Failure to comply with these social functions may result in punishments as provided for in legislation. For Ashley (2002), Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) requires a new approach for companies, including a new mental model for social, economic and political relations. She highlights that CSR should not be limited to a social dimension of the company, but rather seen as part of an integrative vision that encompasses the social, economic and environmental dimensions.

Neto and Froes (2001) argue that CSR involves management that encompasses both internal and external audiences, including active participation in the community. They emphasize that the concept of social responsibility is part of a broader concept, sustainable development.

Mebrato (1998) characterizes CSR as a process that encompasses reputation, ethics and governance, with the objective of minimizing social exclusion. It highlights the importance of considering CSR in relation to sustainable development and taking into account stakeholder expectations.

ISO 26000, launched in 2010, defines CSR as the organization's responsibility for the impacts of its decisions and activities on society and the environment. This includes ethical and transparent behavior that contributes to sustainable development and is consistent with international standards of behavior.

According to Neto and Froes (2001), the concept of

CSR goes beyond legal compliance and philanthropy. CSR is seen as an effort by organizations to curb actions that could harm society or the environment. In this sense, it encompasses citizen responsibility by defining rights, duties and attitudes that generate value for everyone, covering both individuals and legal entities.

Carroll (1979), highlights a range of economic, legal, ethical and philanthropic obligations. Economic responsibility is the foundation of all other dimensions of CSR, and companies must balance profit with obedience to laws, ethics and corporate citizenship. Carroll's pyramid illustrates the four dimensions of CSR, emphasizing that economic performance is the foundation of all other responsibilities.

In this sense, the author points out that the development of companies is intrinsically linked to economic growth, while for others, this relationship is not so close. This development model has the fundamental objective of aligning economic growth with the responsible use of natural resources, environmental protection and concern for social well-being. This approach does not exclude economic growth from development, but it also does not attribute all the merit to the economic aspect. Instead, it seeks an alignment between the two, incorporating two additional dimensions, the ecological-environmental and the social.

This vision of development with an emphasis on social and environmental dimensions began to gain strength in the 1960s. The release of the Club of Rome report in 1972, entitled "The Limits to Growth," and the UN Conference on the Human Environment held in the same year in Stockholm, Sweden, scored crucial points. However, the consolidation of the concept of Sustainable Development only occurred in 1992, during the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development held in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development was adopted, establishing 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) based on the Millennium Development Goals launched in 2000. Thus, by addressing issues such as poverty eradication, gender equality, health, education, reduction of inequalities, climate action, life in water and on land, among others, with the aim of ensuring sustainable development

feasibility, these concepts share several common characteristics and principles that make them relevant in the context of sustainable development. In a complementary way, when observing what Ashley (2002) highlights; Aligrelli (2011); Alves et al. (2015), the convergence between Ecodevelopment and Sustainable Development, based on the aspects: Holistic view: Both concepts consider development as a complex system that involves interactions between different components, recognizing that the economy, society and the environment are intrinsically linked.

Criticism of economic reductionism: Both eco-development and Sustainable Development question the excessive emphasis on economic growth as the only measure of progress, emphasizing the need to evaluate development based on multiple indicators and dimensions.

Long-term vision: Both concepts consider the implications of development on future generations, promoting the notion that sustainable development must meet present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.

Social well-being: Both are concerned with the well-being of communities and seek to reduce social inequalities, promoting a fairer distribution of the benefits of development.

Environmental dimension: They recognize the importance of preserving the environment as an integral part of the development process, promoting the responsible use of natural resources and the minimization of negative environmental impacts. Management of renewable resources: Both eco-development and Sustainable Development advocate the responsible management of natural resources, considering their capacity for regeneration and renewability.

Respect for nature's time: Both concepts value respect for nature's natural cycles, recognizing that the unrestrained exploitation of resources can result in irreversible damage.

Favoring the local and global plan: Both emphasize the importance of promoting sustainable development at local and global levels, recognizing that specific solutions and strategies may vary

according to the characteristics of each region.

Given these aspects, the authors address these similarities, eco-development and Sustainable Development, as a common approach to development that seeks to balance economic, social and environmental dimensions. The importance of covering these three dimensions is fundamental to guarantee truly sustainable development, which meets the needs of the present without compromising the future, respecting the interconnection between economy, society and the environment. This three-dimensional perspective can be fundamental to building a more equitable and environmentally responsible future.

The ethics of Social Responsibility in Companies

The issue that emerges from the ethical issue in companies involves a type of Corporate Social Responsibility, which can be a recognition that a company, corporation or business organization has social, cultural and environmental responsibilities towards the community in which it seeks to operate. This type of corporate citizenship involves an organization accepting the need to better fulfill its responsibilities in order to establish and maintain sustainable success for the organization.

According to Chiavenato (1999), social responsibility is an approach in which companies recognize their impact on society and seek to mitigate this negative impact, while at the same time contributing positively to the sustainable development of the communities in which they operate. For the author, many companies adopt social responsibility practices to not only achieve their own objectives, but also as a way of giving back to society and meeting the ethical and moral expectations of the community in general.

According to Sant'Anna (2015), in recent years there have been changes in the commitment to corporate social responsibility, which indicates:

Requirements at a business level are changing, a few years ago, some companies said they acted responsibly and ethically, now, they cannot just talk about it, it is necessary to put it into practice or they will be punished. Stakeholders do not just accept a logo or a seal indicating that the company

transparency.

According to Neto and Froes (2001), some of the central elements of citizenship do not seem to apply directly to corporations. For example, “citizenship” typically implies membership of a state and an identity similar to national identity; but this connotation of citizenship is obviously problematic for corporations. However, the language of citizenship helps focus our attention on various legal and political virtues of corporations—topics that have been largely neglected by discussions under other headings, such as CSR or sustainability. Garcia (1999), highlights that the ethics of responsibility is related to business ethics, highlighting the importance of considering the social consequences of business actions and decisions. The author points out that the ethics of responsibility requires companies to foresee and consider the possible consequences of their actions, respecting current moral and ethical precepts, as opposed to the ethics of ultimate purposes, which seeks exclusively profit, regardless of social consequences.

According to Ashley (2002), ethics stands out with the need for companies to consider the consequences of their actions in the exploitation of natural resources and the importance of preserving the environment. This not only has a cost, but also represents a fundamental duty, since the environment is a fundamental right for everyone. In this sense, the author signals awareness and changes in business behavior in relation to environmental preservation can lead to a revolution in the behavior of all companies, promoting a more responsible and sustainable approach.

Neto and Froes (2001), point out that the environment as a fundamental right and a fundamental duty, it is essential to promote awareness and responsibility, sharing the burden of preserving the environment and, at the same time, reducing inequalities in the competitive capacity between responsible and non-responsible companies. This approach emphasizes the importance of ethical and environmental responsibility for companies in the search for a fairer and more sustainable society.

Corporate social responsibility is a concept that is based on the idea that companies have a role beyond the simple objective of making a profit; they also have a commitment to society and the environment in which they operate.

In this context, ethical conduct in companies plays

a fundamental role in building solid corporate social responsibility. Business ethics are not limited to compliance with legal standards, but go further, encompassing the adoption of behaviors that benefit society and the environment. Companies that act ethically not only follow the laws, but also consider the social and environmental impacts of their actions.

Corporate social responsibility encompasses the notion that companies must act in a way that benefits the community in which they operate. This includes practices such as creating jobs, paying taxes, promoting social causes and preserving the environment. When companies adopt ethical conduct, they contribute significantly to achieving these objectives.

Corporate Social Responsibility in Brazil

According to Guimaraes (1984), CSR is based on the premise that organizations have direct responsibility and the ability to address social problems. For the author, companies are not only economic entities, but they also play a role in improving the living conditions of society.

Rico (1998), introduces the concept of corporate citizenship, which goes beyond fulfilling the company’s economic function. The author highlights that corporate citizenship presupposes that the company is co-responsible for the well-being of the community.

Soutello Alves (2001) defines corporate citizenship as a set of principles and management systems aimed at creating or preserving value for society. This concept involves the development of socially responsible management methods that meet society’s desires.

According to Soutello Alves (2001), with a corporate-citizen culture, companies assume commitment and define policies in relation to their partners. It practices a set of values that preserve and respect the interests of the parties with which it has a direct and indirect relationship. According to the author, these companies are proactive in the search for solutions to social problems, mobilizing resources in various ways, such as information, management techniques and financial resources.

According to Reis (2007), Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Brazil gained prominence throughout the 1990s, which was driven by the country’s redemocratization and economic opening,

to Sales (2012), the development of CSR actions is also rooted in philanthropic initiatives that some companies previously carried out, and these benevolent activities continue to be an important part of the concept.

According to Camargo et al. (2002), the creation of institutions such as the ABRINQ Foundation for the Rights of Children and Adolescents, the Brazilian Association of Businessmen for Citizenship (CIVES) and the Ethos Institute played significant roles in promoting CSR in the country. For Sartore (2012), the creation of the Corporate Sustainability Index (ISE) on the São Paulo Stock Exchange in 2005 and the inclusion of social responsibility metrics in business rankings demonstrate the growing importance of CSR in the Brazilian business context.

Sartore (2012), points out that although the CSR adoption model in Brazil is different from the process in the United States, with a greater focus on the inclusion of philanthropic actions, it is evident that the synergy of several factors and events contributed to the strengthening and dissemination of CSR practices in the country.

The concepts of CSR in Brazil, the Ethos Institute established a widely adopted definition, which defines it as “the form of management that is defined by the company’s ethical and transparent relationship with all the publics with which it interacts and by the establishment of goals businesses that drive the sustainable development of society, preserving environmental and cultural resources for future generations, respecting diversity and promoting the reduction of social inequalities” (Instituto Ethos, 2009). However, according to Reis (2009), there are several different interpretations and approaches to CSR in Brazil, including social action, private social investment, corporate philanthropy, corporate governance and social responsibility. For the author, these diverse approaches reflect the different ways in which companies in Brazil approach CSR, from philanthropic actions to a commitment to promoting sustainable development and reducing social inequalities.

CONCLUSION

Given the scenario that we see the importance of responsibility in companies, seen within the spectrum of CSR, in which over time, highlighting its roots, the growing awareness of the need for ethical and responsible business practices and the convergence of different approaches and concepts related to the topic.

However, an explanation of how the notion of CSR emerged in response to growing social demands for greater environmental responsibility and improvements in society’s quality of life. The United Nations Conference on Environment and Development, Rio/92, emphasized the importance of companies in sustainable development and the need for ethical and responsible practices.

He also highlights the duality of companies, which must not only seek profit, but also have social functions defined by the State and ethical principles. Failure to fulfill these social functions may result in legal punishments.

The CSR approach has developed over time, incorporating several frameworks, including documents such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the OECD Guidelines for Multinationals, ISO standards and other initiatives. This demonstrates the growing awareness of the importance of the social, economic and environmental dimensions of CSR.

The relationship between eco-development and Sustainable Development is explored, emphasizing the importance of a holistic, long-term vision, social well-being and responsible management of natural resources. These approaches seek to balance economic growth with environmental preservation and social justice.

Ethics plays a central role in CSR, encouraging companies to consider the social and environmental consequences of their actions. In addition to complying with laws, ethical companies adopt practices that benefit society and the environment. By observing the evolution of CSR in Brazil, highlighting the influence of institutions such as the Ethos Institute, the development of corporate sustainability indices and different interpretations of CSR, including social action, philanthropy and commitment to sustainable development. Be how companies that adopt stronger CSR practices can

to the authors' understanding, if it is approached as a genuine commitment to ethical and responsible business practices. Companies seeking long-term benefits from CSR often integrate these principles into their corporate culture and strategy.

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